

Global Film Production

Angelo Leogrande, LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU,
leogrande.cultore@lum.it

The variable "National films per million inhabitants (aged 15-69)" represents an indicator that measures the number of films produced by a particular nation in relation to its active population, i.e., those aged between 15 and 69 years. This indicator allows for an evaluation of a nation's capacity to produce films relative to the size of its population, offering a more accurate picture of the vitality of its film sector compared to merely considering total film production. The decision to focus on the 15-69 age group is intentional, as it corresponds to the segment of the population with the greatest economic, cultural, and creative participation. This group includes the majority of those directly involved in film production, such as directors, actors, and technicians, as well as the primary audience for these films. Therefore, this variable is particularly useful for understanding not only film production but also a country's ability to support and sustain a relevant national film industry in terms of cultural content. More broadly, the ratio of the number of national films produced to the population helps contextualize the level of development of the film industry in countries of various sizes. For example, nations with a relatively small population may have significant production levels when compared to their number of inhabitants, suggesting a highly active creative sector. Conversely, nations with larger populations may have relatively low production, indicating challenges in the film industry or the dominance of foreign content in the domestic market. In summary, this variable is a useful indicator for analyzing the health and vitality of a country's film industry in relation to its active and cultural population. The data refers to the period between 2013 and 2022.

Global Film Production in 2022. The data on national films produced per million inhabitants in the 15-69 age group in 2022 provides an interesting overview of global film production, highlighting how some countries are particularly active in the sector, while others have very limited production. This variable offers a snapshot of the cultural and economic dynamics underlying each country's film industry. At the top of the rankings is Iceland, with 100 films produced per million inhabitants, an extraordinary figure that reflects the importance of national cinema for this small country. Despite its small population, Iceland boasts a vibrant film industry, thanks to public support policies and a strong cultural identity that values local productions. Estonia and Latvia, with 51.2 and 50 films respectively, follow a similar pattern of small countries that invest significantly in their film industries. These Northern European and Baltic countries demonstrate that a small population is not necessarily a barrier to cultural production, and that incentive policies and public support can make a difference. Other European countries with a significant film industry relative to their population include the Czech Republic, with 42.8 films, Luxembourg (41.1), and Finland (39.7). These countries show a strong commitment to promoting culture and the arts, with cinema representing an important part of their national identity. Even larger countries such as Spain (36.3) and Italy (34.6) have substantial film production, indicating a well-developed film sector integrated into cultural and commercial dynamics. Asia is well represented in this ranking, with Japan (38.5) and South Korea (38) among the countries with the highest production per million inhabitants. These figures highlight the growing importance of Asian film industries, which not only produce films for their domestic markets but also have a strong impact on the global scene, especially with high-quality films that often receive international recognition. Countries like France (25.3) and Germany (19) show more modest film production relative to their population, but it is still significant. These countries, historically major players in world cinema, maintain a solid industry, although the lower figures compared to smaller nations might suggest greater international competition or a saturated domestic market. It is

interesting to note that countries with large populations, such as the United States (16), India (11.3), and China (3.8), produce a relatively low number of films per million inhabitants. However, the absolute number of films produced in these countries remains very high due to their vast populations. These film markets are dominated by large commercial productions, and the figures may reflect a greater concentration of resources in a few major productions rather than a more evenly distributed film output. At the lower end of the rankings, we find countries like Egypt (1.5), Ukraine (1.6), and Tunisia (0.4), where film production is very limited. This may be due to various factors, including political instability, lack of funding, or inadequate film infrastructure. The low production in these countries highlights the challenges their local film industries face in competing with international cinema and overcoming economic and political barriers. In summary, the data shows a wide disparity in film production across different countries, influenced by cultural, economic, and political factors. While small Northern European countries and some Asian nations show surprisingly high production relative to their populations, larger countries tend to focus on a few high-profile productions, leaving less room for smaller-scale films.

Global Film Production in 2013-2022. The data on national film production per million inhabitants in the 15-69 age group between 2013 and 2022 highlights significant dynamics in the film industry of various countries. The variations reveal a clear divide between countries that experienced an increase in production and others that saw sharp declines, reflecting structural and cultural changes in the global film industry. A positive example is Lithuania, which saw an increase of 132%, rising from 15.6 to 36.2 films per million inhabitants. This likely reflects investments in the cultural sector and a growing focus on national cinema as a tool for cultural expression and international promotion. Latvia also saw an increase, though more modest (24.38%), showing a similar trend in strengthening its film production. On the other hand, some countries with already high production levels, such as Iceland, maintained steady levels (100 films per million inhabitants), suggesting that they have reached a mature stage in their film industry. However, maintaining this high level is noteworthy, especially given Iceland's small population. Several countries, however, show a worrying decline in film production. Italy, for instance, experienced a 13.5% decrease, dropping from 40 to 34.6 films per million inhabitants. This decline could reflect stagnation or reduced public investment in the film sector, or growing competition from international productions dominating the domestic market. Other European countries, such as the Czech Republic (-13.71%) and Spain (-28.4%), experienced similar declines, indicating common difficulties among many European nations. Particularly striking is the decline in countries like Estonia (-27.17%) and Sweden (-32.89%), which historically had robust film production. These drops can be attributed to a combination of factors, including reduced government financial support, competition with international streaming platforms, and the challenge of sustaining a national film industry in an increasingly competitive global market. Some countries have faced extremely drastic declines, such as Luxembourg (-58.73%) and Switzerland (-79.67%). These figures indicate a significant reduction in the ability to produce national films, possibly due to shifts in economic or cultural priorities, or a local film market that can no longer compete with foreign productions. Emerging nations like Turkey (-51.34%) and India (-53.11%) also experienced major contractions, suggesting that the rapid growth of previous years may have encountered obstacles, such as economic issues or less favorable policies for the film sector. Finally, the cases of countries like Kazakhstan (-95.79%) and Azerbaijan (-97.83%) show an almost complete collapse in national film production. These data point to deep economic or political difficulties that have drastically reduced these countries' ability to produce cultural content, with potential negative consequences for national culture and creative expression. In summary, the data reveals a global film sector undergoing significant transformation, where some countries have managed to maintain or increase their

production, while others have experienced drastic declines, often due to economic, cultural, or political factors limiting their ability to sustain a vibrant film industry.

Conclusions. The value of global film production decreased on average between 2013 and 2022, from a total of 39.61 units to a value of 19.24 units, representing a reduction of -51.41%. The top performers include Lithuania with +32.05%, Latvia with +24.38%, Iceland with a change of 0.00%, Italy with -13.50%, and the Czech Republic with -13.50%. The worst performers are Serbia with -94.84%, Kazakhstan with -95.79%, Azerbaijan with -97.83%, Tunisia with -98.28%, and Peru with -98.88%.

Performance	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Lithuania	15,60	36,20	20,60	132,05
	Latvia	40,20	50,00	9,80	24,38
	Iceland	100,00	100,00	0,00	0,00
	Italy	40,00	34,60	-5,40	-13,50
	Czechia	49,60	42,80	-6,80	-13,71
Worse Performers	Serbia	42,60	2,20	-40,40	-94,84
	Kazakhstan	19,00	0,80	-18,20	-95,79
	Azerbaijan	83,10	1,80	-81,30	-97,83
	Tunisia	23,30	0,40	-22,90	-98,28
	Peru	8,90	0,10	-8,80	-98,88

References

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Angelo, L., & Matarrese, M. M. (2023). The intellectual assets in Europe. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 27(2), 1-13.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2021). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach. *Applied econometrics and international development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.
- Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.
- Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.
- Angelo, L., Laureti, L., & Alberto, C. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. *Available at SSRN 4021150*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3983218*.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Ease of Doing Business in the ESG Framework at World Level. *Available at SSRN 4420946*.
- Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. *Available at SSRN 4398483*.
- Leogrande, A. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. *International Web Post*.
- Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

